

THE FORMATION OF NATIONAL PRESS IN TURKESTAN

Ko'palov Diyorbek Xamro o'g'li

Urganch State University named after Abu Rayhan Biruni, Student

e-mail: kopalovdiyorbek012@gmail.com +99891-919-91-90

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20069288>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 28th April 2026

Accepted: 05th May 2026

Online: 06th May 2026

KEYWORDS

Newspaper, magazine,
press, jadid, Turkestan,
Ismail Obidov,
Makhmudkhodja
Bekhbudi, Munavvar Kari
Abdurashidkhanov.

ABSTRACT

This article examines the formation of the national press in Turkestan in the late 19th and early 20th centuries. It analyzes the emergence of the first newspapers and magazines, as well as their role in promoting enlightenment ideas, advancing education, and shaping national identity. Particular attention is given to the activities of representatives of the Jadid movement, highlighting their use of the press as a tool for raising public awareness. According to the Jadids, the press was the most important means of exerting ideological influence on the broader public.

Introduction.

According to Adeeb Khalid, two factors hindered the development of an independent national press in Turkestan. The first was economic underdevelopment, and the second was pressure from the official government. Although a group of local intellectuals emerged in the late XIX century with the aim of implementing reforms in certain aspects of Turkestan's social life, they were only able to establish themselves firmly in the first decade of the XX century. This delay was likely one of the main reasons for the late emergence of the national press in Turkestan.

The people of Turkestan differed significantly in their mindset and way of thinking from other Muslim communities within the Russian Empire. Due to their highly conservative views and strong

adherence to traditions, newspapers did not gain widespread popularity among the general population. As a result of these factors, most of the national press that emerged in the 10s of the XX century was forced to cease operations. The 1905 Russian bourgeois-democratic revolution struck a blow to the despotic and military-police colonial system in Turkestan. The manifesto declared on October 17 proclaimed that Russian citizens were granted freedoms. It also promised the colonized peoples the right to live freely, gain education and skills, and have their own national press. Encouraged by this, progressive intellectuals began publishing newspapers and magazines under new names.

Literature Review and Methodology.

After the 1905 manifesto, the press in Turkestan rapidly went through a significant transformation within a historically short period, leading to the publication of numerous newspapers and magazines. One of the first to analyze and comment on this was Cho'lpon. In his article *The History of Early Uzbek Periodical Press*, Abdulla Avloni stated that between 1905 and 1917, 22 newspapers and 8 magazines were published in the region in the Uzbek language. According to Ziyoyev's 1927 study *Materials on the History of the Uzbek Periodical Press (1870–1927)*, during this period, 45 newspapers and 36 magazines were published. This information has also been referenced in studies related to press history.

One of the most effective forms of integration of Central Asian reformers was the national periodical press, which began to form at the end of the XIX century and developed rapidly at the beginning of the XX century, despite the endless control and prohibitions of the tsarist regime. According to the Jadids, the press was the most important means of ideological influence on the consciousness of broad layers of society. As one of the Turkestan progressives wrote, "Without the national press, there is no nation itself." For them, the press was a kind of tribune through which they conveyed their ideas of social renewal to the masses. During the first decades of the XX century, in Central Asia, with their direct participation, such newspapers and magazines as "Tarakkiy", "Khurshid" (1906), "Osiyo", "Tuzhzhor", "Shukhrat" (1907), "Turon", "Bukhoroi Sharif" (1912), "Oyina", "Samarkand" (1913), "Sadoi Fargona", and "Sadoi Turkiston"

(1914–1915) were opened. On the basis of a new wave of enlightenment in 1917, such printed organs as "Khurriyat", "Nazhot", "Kengash", "Turon", and "Ulug Turkiston" were organized. These newspapers were already conducting propaganda of a broad program of political reforms.

In total, there were more than 15 of them, and this was already a great ideological force. The range of topics was very wide, from educational to political. The national press clearly demonstrated the presence in the region of a new type of person, with progressive thinking, caring about the welfare of the nation, and fighting inertia, backwardness, and ignorance.

Analysis and Results.

The history of the national press began on June 27, 1906, when Tashkent progressives led by Ismail Obidov (Gabitov) began publishing the first newspaper in the Uzbek language, "Tarakkiy" ("Progress"). After the revolution of 1905, he left for the Turkestan region. Already in Tashkent, under the strong influence of the revolutionary events taking place around him, together with progressive representatives of education and culture Munavvar Kari Abdurashidov, Abdulla Avloni, Mahmudhoja Behbudi, and others, he began publishing a newspaper in the Uzbek language, "Tarakkiy" ("Progress"), the first issue of which was published on June 14 (27), 1906. The newspaper immediately began to propagate the ideas of freedom, equality, and friendship of peoples and opposed the colonial policy of tsarism. In one of his editorials, I. Gabitov wrote that although freedom of speech was declared

in the Manifesto of the Russian Emperor on October 17, real "freedom" in Turkestan still existed only on paper. And the tsarist censorship, closely monitoring every printed publication, continues to cross out any word that is not pleasing to it, not to mention freedom-loving or independent thoughts.

After the closure of the newspaper "Tarakkiy" in September 1906, the newspaper "Khurshid" ("Sun") began to be published under the editorship of Munavvar Kari Abdurashidkhanov. From September 6 to November 16, 1906, only 11 issues were published. The newspaper objectively covered the economic, socio-political, and cultural processes taking place in the region and the current problems of Turkestan society. Articles from the series "New Schools and Madrassas in Turkestan" were regularly published on the pages of "Khurshid", promoting the ideas of education and spirituality among the population. The newspaper paid much attention to school reforms, the need to transform the life and culture of Turkestan society. In one of the editorials, in particular, it was said that the newspaper was pursuing the goal of proving the incorrectness of the assertion that there is no and cannot be unity among Muslims.

Merchant Saidkarim Saidazimbay published the newspaper "Tuzhzhor", with its first issue released on August 27, 1907. The newspaper focused primarily on promoting new commercial and trade relations while also providing economic education. A total of 36 issues were published before it was shut down in 1908. The next publication aligned with the Jadid movement was the newspaper Osiyo ("Asia"), which was launched on

April 9, 1908, in Tashkent. It was published in the Uzbek language twice a week, with Akhmadjon Bektemirov (Muhammadjon) serving as its editor.

Initially, the printed organs of the national-progressive movement operated only in Tashkent. However, starting in 1912, newspapers began to be published in other cities of Turkestan. In Bukhara, for instance, the newspapers "Bukhoroi Sharif" ("Sacred Bukhara"), founded by the Azerbaijani Mirzo Jalol Yusufzade, and "Turon", edited by G. Husayni, were published. The enlighteners of Bukhara placed great hopes on the daily newspaper as an important means of propaganda and agitation of new ideas. With such intentions, the first issue of "Bukhoroi Sharif" was published at the initiative of young Bukharans, with the primary goal of "spreading civilization and the idea of unity." Interestingly, as early as 1906, the Azerbaijani magazine "Molla Nasreddin" had noted the Bukhara population's interest in the periodical press and had even suggested naming a future Bukhara newspaper "Gaflat" ("Backwardness"). "Bukhoroi Sharif" was printed in Kagan at the printing house of L. N. Levi (Levin) in a large format of four pages. From March 11, 1912, to January 2, 1913, a total of 153 issues were published.

Under the editorship of Makhmudkhodja Bekhbudi, the newspaper "Samarkand" or "New Samarkand" and the first magazine, "Oyina" ("Mirror") were published. The newspaper "Samarkand" was one of the first bilingual newspapers in Turkestan. Since April 1913, 45 issues have been published. The newspaper was released twice a week and distributed throughout

Central Asia. The representative of the newspaper in Khojent was Mirzokhid Mirokilov, and in the Samarkand region, Akbar Shokhmansurov. After the publication of the 26th and 27th issues of the newspaper titled "New Samarkand," starting from the 28th issue, it resumed publication under its former name, "Samarkand". The main creation of Mahmudkhodja Behbudi, the magazine "Oyina," is a vivid monument to his ideas and vigorous activity. The first issue of the magazine was published on August 20, 1913. A total of 52 issues, stored in the National Library of Uzbekistan named after Alisher Navoi, comprise 1256 pages. In total, 68 issues were published. The magazine was released weekly, with each issue containing about 24 pages. Starting from the 47th issue, photo illustrations began to be included. Most of them depicted the architectural monuments of Samarkand and the stops on M. Behbudi's journey, and several photographs of Ismail Gasprinsky were published. In the idea of creating "Oyina," Mahmudkhodja Behbudi relied on the experience of his teachers. It is known that Ismail Gasprinsky, before publishing the newspaper "Tarjimon," issued leaflets under the name "Mir'oti jadid" — "New mirror," and Qazi Abdurashid Ibrahimov published the reformist-regional magazine "Mir'oti-Kozgu" in 1902-1909. In Azerbaijan, an artistic magazine with the same name was published in 1910.

In 1914-1915, under the editorship of Ubaidulla Khodjaev, the newspaper "Sadoi Turkiston" (Voice of Turkestan) was published. Following "Sadoi Turkiston", the newspaper "Sadoi Fargona" (Voice of Fergana) began to be published. Its first issue was published on April 3, 1914. It was the first newspaper in the Fergana Valley, the publisher and editor of which was Obidjan Makhmudov, a Kokand entrepreneur and industrialist, a famous educator who united the progressive intelligentsia of Kokand around himself.

Conclusion.

There is no doubt that the Uzbek periodical press from 1905 to 1917 provides extensive material for studying the economic, socio-political, and religious-educational conditions of that turbulent era, as well as how reformist ideas emerged and developed.

Had the Uzbek periodical press not existed during the years under study, accurately assessing the socio-political and religious-educational life of that period would have been considerably more difficult.

Unprecedented for the Turkestan region, mass media in the form of magazines and newspapers shook society's life in the early XX century. Collectively, the periodical press of the new formation played a huge role in enlightening the population, awakening new ideas in the consciousness of the youth of Central Asia, and promoting education.

References:

1. Ziyoy Said. O'zbek vaqtli matbuoti tarixiga materiallar (1870-1927). - Toshkent Samarqand: O'zbekiston davlat nashriyoti, 1927. - B. 43.

2. Ernazarov T. Turkistonda vaqtli matbuot (1870-1924-yillar). – Toshkent: O'zbekiston SSR davlat nashriyoti, 1959. – B. 7.
3. Khalid, Adeeb. The Politics... – P.121.
4. Said, Ziya. O'zbek vaqtli matbuoti tarixiga materiallar. 1870 – 1917. – Tashkent - Samarqand:
5. Abduazizova, N. Turkiston matbuoti tarixi (1870 – 1917). – Toshkent: Akademiya, 2000; Abduazizova, N. O'zbekiston jurnalistikasi tarixi. Toshkent, 2009. 27
6. Khalid, Adeeb. Printing, Publishing, and Reform in Tsarist Central Asia // International Journal of Middle East Studies, Vol. 26, No. 2. (May, 1994), – P.187.
7. Abdulla Avloniy. Burungi o'zbek vaqtli matbuotining tarixi.
8. Абдуазизова Н.А. Туркистон матбуоти тарихи (1870 – 1917 йй.). – Т.: Академия, 2000. – Б. 45
9. Авлоний А. Бурунги ўзбек вақтли матбуотининг тарихи. (наш. тай. Ш.Ризаев) // Миллий уйғониш. – Т.: Университет, 1993. – 115-123 б.
10. Чўлпон. Туркистонда матбуот // Жамият ва бошқарув. – Тошкент, 1998. – №. 2 (Наш. тай. Т.Тоғаев)
11. Ernazarov T. Time press in Turkestan (1870-1924 years). - Tashkent: State publishing house of the Uzbek SSR, 1959. - P. 7.
12. Cholpon. Press in Turkestan. "Society and Management", 1998, No. 2, pp. 40-44.
13. Ochilov N. Periodical press // National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan. J.12. -Т.: O'ZME publishing house. 2006. -B.227.
14. Авлоний А. Танланган асарлар. 1-жилд. Тошкент: «Маънавият», 1998.